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The ATLAS ITk Strip Detector for the Phase-II LHC Upgrade

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Abstract

The inner detector of the present ATLAS experiment has been designed and developed to function in the environment of the present Large Hadron Collider (LHC). At the ATLAS Phase-II Upgrade, the particle densities and radiation levels will exceed current levels by a factor of ten. The instantaneous luminosity is expected to reach unprecedented values, resulting in up to 200 proton-proton interactions in a typical bunch crossing. The new detectors must be faster and they need to be more highly segmented. The sensors used also need to be far more resistant to radiation, and they require much greater power delivery to the front-end systems. At the same time, they cannot introduce excess material which could undermine tracking performance. For those reasons, the inner tracker of the ATLAS detector was redesigned and will be rebuilt completely.

The ATLAS Upgrade Inner Tracker (ITk) consists of several layers of silicon particle detectors. The innermost layers will be composed of silicon pixel sensors, and the outer layers will consist of silicon microstrip sensors. This contribution focuses on the strip region of the ITk. The central part of the strip tracker (barrel) will be composed of rectangular short (~ 2.5 cm) and long (~ 5 cm) strip sensors. The forward regions of the strip tracker (end-caps) consist of six disks per side, with trapezoidal shaped sensors of various lengths and strip pitches. After the completion of final design reviews in key areas, such as Sensors, Modules, Front-End electronics, and ASICs, a large scale prototyping program has been completed in all areas successfully. We present an overview of the Strip System and highlight the final design choices of sensors, module designs and ASICs. We will summarise results achieved during prototyping and the current status of pre-production and production on various detector components, with an emphasis on QA and QC procedures.

1 Introduction

The ATLAS experiment[1] will replace the inner detector system at the end of run 3 during the Phase-II Upgrade, to be able to detect higher particle densities and withstand higher radiation damage. The upgrade will reach an instantaneous luminosity of $7.5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ that is the result of 200 proton-proton interactions for bunch crossing. The ATLAS inner detector (Inner Tracker ITk) covers a radius from $400 < z < 1000 \text{ mm}$, it will be fully made of silicon detectors, the system closer to the beam being pixels and the outer most layers covered with microstrips. Figure 1 shows a representation of the ITk Phase-II upgrade, detailing the barrel and end-cap position of the strip detector.

Figure 1: Sketch of the ITk ATLAS Phase-II upgrade[2]

The ITk strip detector consist of two parts, the barrel and the end-cap. The barrel has rectangular shaped microstrips sensors with two lengths, short ($\sim 2.5 \text{ cm}$) and long ($\sim 5 \text{ cm}$). The stave is the barrel structure that holds 28 modules. The staves surround the interaction region in a cylindrical configuration. The end-cap has 6 differently shaped strip modules which are loaded onto a petal, a trapezoidal structure that holds 12 modules. The end-cap microstrips are pointing towards the beam therefore they are not parallel. The end-cap modules are labelled from R0 (closest to the beam) to R5 (outermost module). R3, R4 and R5 are split modules, where each module consist of two sensors. The composition of 32 petals displayed in circular shape creates one end-cap disc, and the full end-cap consist of 12 discs (6 each side) that will be located in the forward region of the ITk. During the run time of the high-luminosity LHC the ITk will have to withstand the accumulated radiation of $8 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ and the thermal stress created by the operating temperature of $-35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the shut-down periods at room temperature.

The staves and petals hold a titanium pipe flowing a bi-phase CO_2 for cooling the modules, reducing the leakage current after irradiation (to manageable levels). Details of the Phase-II upgrades are described in Reference [2]. Figure 2 shows a sketch of a petal and stave. Once the strip barrel and end-cap are built, as well as the pixel system, they will be introduced in the ATLAS experiment replacing the current inner tracker.

2 ATLAS ITk Strip Detector Components

2.1 Sensors

The sensors for the barrel and the end-cap are produced at Hamamatsu Photonics. The sensor production currently is on schedule reaching 50 % of the full production.

Previous results showed that the interstrip resistance decreases due to the accumulation of electric charge on the surface of the sensors[3]. To minimize the accumulated surface charge, the

Figure 2: Sketch of petal (top) and stave (bottom) with their modules and End of Substructure (EoS) cards[2].

ITk strip collaboration is taking precaution during shipment and transport. The use of ionic guns or ultraviolet lights helps removing this undesired surface charge.

2.2 ASICs

The module has three main ASIC components (Figure 3 shows a picture of a module with the ASICs):

- ABCStar (ATLAS Binary Chip)
- HCCStar (Hybrid Control Chip)
- AMACStar (Autonomous Monitor and Control Chip)

The ABCStar is the strips read out chip, it is a binary chip that gives the information of the hit. HCCStar controls the ABCStar readout for the same module. ABCStar and HCCStar are on the hybrids. The AMACStar, located on the power board, provides both monitoring and interrupt functionality. Final versions of all chips are approved and in production.

The ASICs suffer a the Total Ionising Dose (TID) bump, an increase of the power consumption due to radiation, which is mitigated pre-irradiating the chips after the TID bump (with gamma irradiation minimum dose of 5 Mrad and maximum of 8 Mrad), therefore, there is no increase in the power consumption during data taking. First prototypes of the ASICs being tested have shown that the pre-irradiation of the chips was recommended (results shown in Reference [2, 4]). The contract with the pre-irradiating company is finalized.

The ABCStar showed hit loss in certain channels around the SRAM blocks, which could be mitigated by inverting the clock polarity with cross input wirebonds of the HCC.

2.3 Power boards

The system that distributes the power to different parts of the module is called the power board. It has a DCDC converter (bPOL12V), it distributes the high voltage to the sensor and it holds the AMACStar. Final versions of the power board are already in production, since they had to be slightly improved. End-cap power board had to be redesign to reduce the noise to lower levels. The barrel power board was showing extremely high noise when cold (-35°C), against the expected behaviour. After investigation it showed that this noise was due to some capacitors vibrations. Those capacitors have been replaced and do not show the increase of noise when cold. Now final versions are being produced for end-cap and barrel mitigating the noise.

3 Modules

3.1 Module Assembly

The sensor has a HV-tab attached to the backplane to facilitate the high voltage connection, this attachment is done with the wire-bonding machine to achieve stable contact to the backplane metal. Afterwards the power board and the hybrid with the corresponding ASICs are glued on top of the silicon sensor. The glue has to assure great thermal propagation, low noise but to isolate electrically and stand temperatures from 40°C to -35°C , as well as to withstand the end-of-life radiation dose that the sensors will receive and assure that the sensors will not get detached. Several glues have been tested and two fulfil all the requirements. After gluing, the strips have to be individually wire bonded to the ABCStar. Figure 3 shows a picture of an R2 module with the power board and the hybrid glued to it and the HV-tab attached.

Figure 3: Picture of an R2 module from the end-cap.

3.2 Module QA/QC

To ensure the correct performance of the module once it is assembled different tests are run on the module.

Visual inspection is performed for each component once it arrives to each institute, it is done for checking scratches and possible chips after each step. To investigate any defect, scratch or chip or bond issues, a dedicated setup should be capable to capture any of those possible failures with a camera.

Testing each component separately assures the performance of the final module, so individual tests such as current-voltage curves for sensors or noise tests for the hybrids are performed. Once the module is assembled, it is test during thermal cycling to assure proper cold performance and afterwards the module is ready to be loaded to the support structures (petal or stave).

During the module assembly, metrology measurements are taken, to check the hybrid and power board position, glue height and module bow. Those parameters are needed to ensure optimal heat conduction to the coolant as well as a correct bonding of the ABCStar to the sensors. Precise measurement of the glue weight during assembly gives information that the applied glue is sufficient to ensure the thermal conductivity as well as to hold the parts through all the detector lifetime.

4 System test

Once the modules are built, they are loaded to the substructures (petal or stave), and connected to the End of Substructure (EoS) cards (shown in Figure 2). The position of the loaded modules

is recorded to give precise spatial position on the petal and the staves, which is essential for detector alignment.

For assuring the functionality of petals and staves, a system test has been performed successfully for the barrel and about to start for the end-cap. This test checks the good functionality of the cooling system and the End of Substructure card. The end-cap system test is built with 8 petals and the barrel with 4 staves. Those tests show the viability of the structures, substructures and End of Substructures for the future detector. The results of the barrel have been successful and the system test for the end-cap will be done soon.

5 Conclusions

Production is imminent for ATLAS barrel and end-cap of the strip Phase-II upgrade, which are on track to be delivered in time for the insertion of the full ATLAS ITk Phase-II upgrade.

Sensors production is reaching 50 %. Final versions of the ASICs as well as the power boards and hybrids are approved and production is starting for barrel and end-cap modules.

Quality control and assurance tests for each component controls the quality of the module in each step. First petals and staves were mounted for the system test. The barrel system test was successful and the end-cap system test is soon to be done.

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